

Evaluating Financial Literacy among Library and Information Science Undergraduates at the National Open University of Nigeria

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Abstract

Purpose of the Study: *This study investigates the perception of financial literacy among undergraduate library and information science students of the National Open University of Nigeria.*

Methodology: *The study employed a descriptive survey design. The population comprised seven hundred and ninety-five (795) undergraduate students of the Department of Library and Information Science, National Open University of Nigeria, spread across the 109 study centres of the institution. The total enumeration sampling technique was adopted. The instrument for data collection was a structured Google Form questionnaire which was distributed to each student via their emails. Five hundred and sixty-four (564) responses were received. Collected data were analysed with frequency, percentage and mean score and presented in tables.*

Findings: *The results reveal that the respondents perceive their level of financial literacy as satisfactory. Nonetheless, gaps remain in areas such as tax-related knowledge and investment planning. It also reveals that while financial behaviours such as maintaining savings accounts and budgeting are common, debt management practices could improve. Furthermore, a significant majority of students recognise the importance of formal financial literacy education, and express a strong need for comprehensive instruction on financial topics including credit management, investing, and tax planning.*

Recommendations/Conclusion: *The findings underscore the necessity for targeted educational interventions to enhance financial literacy and support effective financial practices among students.*

Study Type: *Empirical study*

Keywords: Financial behaviour, financial literacy, financial knowledge, library and information science undergraduates, National Open University of Nigeria

Introduction

Financial literacy skills are critical for successful navigation of complex 21st-century financial terrains because they are the knowledge and skills one requires to make sound financial decisions. It is the ability of one to obtain, understand, and evaluate the relevant information necessary to make financial decisions (Mason and Wilson, 2000; Hung, Parker, and Yoong, 2009). That is why it is recommended that studies be conducted among groups to understand whether they are equipped to effectively navigate the maze of financial decisions they must make every day (Lucardi, 2019). One such group worth investigating is university students. Because university students make many financial decisions that can

have serious consequences throughout their lives (Lusardi, 2015b), they should have adequate levels of financial literacy that can help them achieve a better standard of living and promote their well-being (Hussain and Sajjad, 2016). This study evaluates the financial literacy levels among undergraduate library and information science students in Nigeria, focusing on students of the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN). As an open and distance learning (ODL) institution, NOUN's student population is largely comprised of married and employed adults who are responsible for not only their tuition and other school-related expenses but also their families. In effect, many students of NOUN juggle several roles and responsibilities. Segbenya and Anokye (2022) suggest that because of their many roles and responsibilities, ODL students often experience psychological, socio-religious, and financial or economic challenges, which can result in work, academic, and life-balance-related challenges. Furthermore, even unmarried and unemployed ODL students mostly depend on their families for their expenses in school. Unarguably, their source(s) is not inexhaustible; therefore, the ability to handle their financial matters will contribute to their well-being. Unfortunately, while financial literacy is among the life skills that individuals are encouraged to possess, in Nigeria as in most other developing countries, it is rarely taught at home and in schools (Fanta & Mutsonziwa, 2014). As a result, "a high percentage of Nigerians are unable to manage their financial resources effectively (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2018). The researchers' interest in studying financial literacy among undergraduate students arises from a general observation of a deficiency in financial literacy studies among this population in Nigeria. Additionally, there is a noticeable dearth of literature on financial literacy in the Nigerian library and information science field. Invariably, the results of this study will not only give an insight into the financial behaviours and practices among students in an open and distance learning institution and Nigeria in general. It will also enrich the literature on librarianship and hopefully stimulate more research interest in this direction. It is also hoped that the results of this study will provide some insights for some intervention in financial literacy education by the university management.

Research Objectives

The general objective of this study is to investigate financial literacy among undergraduate library and information science students of the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN). Specifically, the study seeks to do the following:

1. Ascertain the perceived levels of knowledge of personal finance among undergraduate library and information science students of the National Open University of Nigeria.
2. Ascertain the perceived levels of financial behaviour among undergraduate library and information science students of the National Open University of Nigeria.
3. Ascertain whether undergraduate library and information science students of the National Open University of Nigeria consider formal financial literacy education important
4. Find out the specific financial literacy topics that undergraduate library and information science students of the National Open University of Nigeria may need more education.
5. Ascertain the perceived challenges to financial literacy among undergraduate library and information science students of the National Open University of Nigeria.
6. Determine the perceived strategies that can enhance financial literacy among undergraduate library and information science students of the National Open University of Nigeria.

Literature Review

There have been many definitions of the term, financial literacy, from the mid-2000s (Faulkner, 2022). Consequently, the term has varying conceptual definitions in existing research, as well as diverse operational definitions and values (Remund, 2010). Remund further notes that in the literature, the definitions of financial literacy generally fall into five categories: (1) knowledge of financial concepts,

(2) ability to communicate about financial concepts, (3) aptitude in managing personal finances, (4) skills in making appropriate financial decisions and (5) confidence in planning effectively for future financial needs. Several definitions have been made along these lines.

OECD (2012) defines the concept as “a combination of financial knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behaviours that people need to make sound financial decisions, based on economic and personal circumstances to improve their financial well-being.” This implies that because peoples’ economic and personal circumstances vary, it is important that at whatever stage one is on their financial journey, they should possess financial literacy skills to manage their finances appropriately for their benefit. CFI Team (2015) conceives the term as the “cognitive understanding of financial components and skills such as budgeting, investing, borrowing, taxation, and personal financial management. When such skills are lacking in an individual(s), they are considered financially illiterate.” Thus, even if an individual(s) possesses any or all of the other kinds of literacy skills, including information literacy, health literacy, etc., they are considered financially illiterate if they lack financial literacy skills because it is a basic skill that enables one to navigate the financial maze on a day-to-day basis (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014). However, financial literacy goes beyond the mere acquisition of financial knowledge. A financially literate individual can interpret and understand basic financial concepts and apply that knowledge to make informed decisions (Remund, 2010). Additionally, the knowledge should be evident in how the individual actively manages their own money from the point of accumulation to consumption. Financial literacy has some measurable components, including saving, budgeting, investing, borrowing, and personal financial management, and it reflects behaviour and attitude.

Some studies have examined the financial behaviour of university students. In an earlier study among undergraduate students at Christian Service University College, Ghana, Acheampong et al. (2015) found that a majority of the students had low-level financial literacy, with an average score of 52.9%. Consequently, a majority of the students were unable to make financial decisions on savings, borrowing, insurance, and investment. A significant relationship between financial literacy and financial behaviour was found among university students in Malaysia, as the students with high financial literacy exhibited well-managed financial behaviour in savings, future planning, and prudent spending. Also, education and financial attitude influence students’ financial literacy (Kamel & Sahid, 2021). Paskelian et al. (2019) and Zulaihati, Susanti & Widyastuti (2020) agree and posit that a high level of financial literacy influences one’s pattern of behaviour in decision-making, price comparisons when buying, budgeting, savings, and investment. Gyimah et al. (2018) found in their study among 480 students across public and technical universities and teacher-training colleges in Ghana that, on average, the students lacked financial knowledge, particularly on insurance. On the other hand, they were financially literate in savings and borrowing.

The detrimental effect of a lack of financial literacy or low financial literacy was revealed in a study among university students in Sri Lanka, where the level of knowledge of the students on savings was medium, and their general knowledge of finance, investment, and insurance was low. The study further revealed that while a majority of the students lacked financial knowledge, students who had more knowledge of financial literacy made good decisions relating to money management in the areas of payments of fuel bills, insurance cover, repairs, and maintenance than those who did not. The study concluded that financial literacy influenced the undergraduates’ investment decisions positively and significantly (Kumari, 2020). Extant literature indicates that many factors influence financial literacy. Yahaya Zainol, Abidin & Ismail (2019) found that students who took financial management courses had higher levels of financial knowledge than those who did not. They also found that financial knowledge significantly influenced financial attitudes, and financial attitudes influenced financial behaviour. Similarly, in South Africa, undergraduates who had taken money management courses and the ones who participated in family finance decision-making were more likely to be financially literate.

Higher levels of financial literacy were noticed among subgroups of the students who financed their education through bank loans, unlike the groups that family financed.

While it is generally agreed that students should be financially literate, it has been suggested that some factors constitute challenges to them. Andreou & Philip (2020) identified the absence of a specialised personal finance course in the teaching curricula of tertiary education institutions in Cyprus. This invariably affected the students' knowledge of financial concepts such as savings, investment, mortgage borrowing, inflation, how to plan for retirement, and practical experience of money matters. They also identified a lack of financial education during the student's secondary school education and inadequate 'hands-on' opportunities as factors that contributed to the poor financial performance of Cypriot students. So, the students who entered the university did not have vital financial knowledge and skill sets to manage finances and make good financial decisions. The researchers noted that the acquisition of knowledge on financial concepts could have helped the students make valuable financial decisions instead of depending on their parents' advice to manage their everyday financial matters. Invariably, this affected their financial behaviour and decision-making. It must be stressed that this is not peculiar to students in Cyprus as other studies have also revealed the absence of financial literacy courses in most universities' curricula and the lack of exposure to financial matters during the early days (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2011; Central Bank of Nigeria, 2018). It is also suggested that teachers lack confidence and so feel inadequate in handling financial literacy classes as they cannot impart the knowledge that they lack (Llewellyn, 2012).

Additionally, the increase in financial products and services from financial institutions has left new and old consumers with enormous offers, creating difficult conditions for efficient decision-making (Spiranec, Zorica, & Simoncic, 2012). Mitchell and Abusheva (2016) outline other challenges in financial literacy, including lack of financial culture, lack of funds from the government, inequality, economic conditions, and biased behaviour that can prevent one from attaining desirable financial well-being. Lack of private resources or insufficient resources is a challenge to financial literacy as found by Delanvande et al. (2008), who posit that people's motivation to acquire financial skills is dependent on the level of their private resources. The implication is that people are motivated to have financial knowledge if they have more resources for investment. This was also corroborated by Monticone (2010), who found that households with larger financial assets were more likely to invest in financial knowledge.

Given the challenges, Ergün, (2017) advocates that more financial literacy courses should be introduced in the university education curriculum to aid students in handling their finances better as well as improve their wellbeing. Kwenda and Sihlongonyane (2021) suggest that university authorities should provide more financial education campaigns to improve the financial management practices of students in developing countries. This is because some of the undergraduates finance their education personally through loans from banks and relatives often resulting in debts. So, there is an urgent need to teach them how to manage and service loans. Azer and Mohamad (2018) believe that academia should teach and lead their students on how best to adapt to a better creditor posture. They also advised school authorities to teach financial literacy on their school's social media platforms since students use them regularly.

The practical application of "personal finance" topics to inculcate good attitudes in students for the enhancement of appropriate financial behaviour and efficient financial decision-making and the long-term well-being of individuals has been suggested (Andreou and Philip, 2018). Oseifuah and Formadi (2018) advise undergraduates to acquire financial literacy by studying budgeting, interest rates, and investment, among other subjects, to help them handle financial management matters. Also, learning financial skills and knowledge about financial investment are thought to be among the factors that enhance undergraduates' investment decisions (Kumari, 2020). University Libraries, University of Maryland (2022) suggests that financial literacy topics for students should include budgeting, credit, investing, savings- banks & banking, student loans, grants, and scholarships, and other/general topics

while Michigan State University Libraries (2022) outline the possible five key money topics for financial literacy to include: earn, borrow, save and invest, spend, and protect, covering all stages of life. The Michigan State University Federal Credit Union (2023) also offers financial education on the following topics: fraud and identity theft, loans, budgeting, home buying, kids and money, and retirement to prepare students to face the realities of life.

Librarians can also get involved in teaching financial literacy to library users. Some financial literacy topics that librarians can teach include money investment, daily money matters, ways of starting enterprises and setting up small businesses, mortgages, loans, credits, and the creation of financial family savings plans. Others are the tax system, financing children's education, retirement savings; health insurance programmes, regaining control of finances in cases of indebtedness, access to relevant and valid financial information, and job and career opportunities (Spiranec, Zorica & Simonic, 2012). They equally stress that financial literacy topics need to be continuously modified according to the users' needs within the financial market and economy.

The university libraries can also support the teaching and learning of financial literacy to undergraduates through acquiring and building collections on banking, budgeting, credit, debt, identity theft, investing, saving and spending, and teen finance, which are useful in university settings (Reiter, 2020). Also, Mitchell and Abusheva (2016) suggest that educational institutions should include the teaching of personal finance courses before graduation. Antoni et al. (2019) advocate for parents to increase financial teaching and monitoring, model financial management behaviour, and reinforce financial management in their children to improve their economic behaviour.

Methodology

A descriptive survey design was used for this study. The population comprised seven hundred and ninety-five (795) undergraduate students of the Department of Library and Information Science, National Open University of Nigeria, spread across the 109 study centres of the institution. Because the population was a manageable number, the total enumeration sampling technique was adopted. The instrument for data collection was a structured Google Form questionnaire, which was distributed to each student via email. The questionnaire explained the purpose of the research and sought the assistance of the receiver to participate in the study by filling out the questionnaire. The data analysis was done with frequencies and percentages and presented in tables.

Result

Research Questions 1-7

Table 2: Mean Responses on the Perceived Level of Personal Financial Knowledge among Respondents

Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
I can create and maintain a personal budget	306 (54.3)	222 (39.4)	28 (5.0)	8 (1.4)	3.46	Agree
I am knowledgeable about saving, credit and debt management	222 (39.4)	287 (50.9)	53 (9.4)	2 (0.4)	3.29	Agree
My overall knowledge of personal finance is high	180 (31.9)	348 (61.7)	23 (4.1)	13 (2.3)	3.23	Agree
I am knowledgeable about investment and retirement planning	212 (37.6)	255 (45.2)	85 (15.1)	12 (2.1)	3.18	Agree
I am knowledgeable about tax laws and regulations	120 (21.3)	305 (54.1)	122 (21.6)	17 (3.0)	2.93	Agree
Overall					2.68	Agree

The results in Table 2 above indicate the mean responses on the perceived level of personal financial knowledge among the respondents. The statements featured covered budgeting, saving, credit and debt management investment and retirement planning, tax laws, and regulations. The results show that the respondents agree that they are knowledgeable in all aspects of personal finance. However, the statement “I can create and maintain a personal budget scored the highest mean (3.46). The overall total mean of 2.68 also indicates that the respondents agree that they are knowledgeable in the indicated aspects of this cluster. This suggests that personal financial knowledge among the respondents is satisfactory. The implication is that the respondents are knowledgeable about the elements of financial literacy investigated.

Table 3: Mean Responses on Financial Behaviour among Respondents

Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
I have a savings account	411 (72.9)	134 (23.8)	19 (3.4)	0 (0.0)	3.71	Strongly Agree
I monitor my expenses regularly	298 (52.8)	228 (40.4)	38 (6.7)	0 (0.0)	3.46	Agree
I budget my finances	342 (60.6)	126 (22.3)	78 (13.8)	18 (3.2)	3.40	Agree
I check my bank statements regularly	212 (37.6)	289 (51.2)	63 (11.2)	0 (0.0)	3.26	Agree
I currently have an outstanding debt	108 (19.1)	259 (45.9)	105 (18.6)	92 (16.3)	2.86	Agree
I sometimes borrow money to pay for education or other expenses	210 (37.2)	110 (19.5)	186 (33.0)	58 (10.3)	2.83	Agree
Overall					2.68	Agree

Table 3 presents the responses to statements on the perceived level of financial behaviour among respondents. The statements cover savings, spending, loans, budgeting and debt management. The data shows that the respondents strongly agree that they have a savings account (Mean=3.71). They agree with the other indicated statements; however, the statement with the lowest mean score is “I sometimes borrow money to pay for education or other expenses”, which suggests that their borrowing level is low. The overall Mean (2.68) indicates that the level of agreement of the respondents with statements on financial behaviour is high. The implication is that the respondents have good financial behaviour and practices.

Table 4: Mean Responses on Formal Literacy Education among Respondents

	Frequency	Valid Percent
Yes	522	92.6
No	42	7.4
Total	564	100.0

It was also thought necessary to find out if the respondents perceive a need for formal financial literacy education. Table 4 presents the study's results on whether the respondents consider formal literacy education important. The results indicate that the majority (522 or 92.6%) consider it important, while only 45 or 7.4% think otherwise.

Table 5: Mean Responses on the Specific Financial Literacy Topics Considered Important

Items	VHN	HN	NN	HNN	Mean	Decision
Credit and Debt Management	272 (48.2)	232 (41.1)	54 (9.6)	6 (1.1)	3.86	Very Highly Needful
Saving and Investing.	344 (61.0)	184 (32.6)	30 (5.3)	6 (1.1)	3.53	Very Highly Needful
Taxes and Tax Planning.	245 (43.4)	221 (39.2)	83 (14.7)	15 (2.7)	3.53	Very Highly Needful
Entrepreneurship and Business Basics	334 (59.2)	203 (36.0)	21 (3.7)	6 (1.1)	3.53	Very Highly Needful
Financial Goal Setting	342 (60.6)	188 (33.3)	24 (4.3)	10 (1.8)	3.52	Very Highly Needful
Budgeting and Financial Planning	323 (57.3)	193 (34.2)	31 (5.5)	17 (3.0)	3.49	Highly Needful
Personal Finance and Career Choice.	315 (55.9)	222 (39.4)	19 (3.4)	8 (1.4)	3.49	Highly Needful
Risk Management and Insurance	278 (49.3)	222 (39.4)	64 (11.3)	0 (0.0)	3.37	Highly Needful
Consumer Awareness	263 (46.6)	248 (44.0)	40 (7.1)	13 (2.3)	3.34	Highly Needful
Overall					3.51	Highly Needful

Research Objective 3 sought to determine the specific topics in financial literacy on which the respondents perceive a need for education. Table 5 above shows that the respondents perceive a very high need for education in credit and debt management (M=3.96), saving and investing, taxes and tax planning and entrepreneurship and business basics with a mean score of 3.53, respectively, and a high need on the other topics. The cluster mean (3.51) indicates that there is a high need for education on the outlined topics in financial literacy.

Table 6: Mean Responses on Perceived Challenges to Financial Literacy among Respondents

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	
Lack of financial knowledge	289 (51.2)	221 (39.2)	47 (8.3)	7 (1.2)	3.40	Agree
Late introduction to financial education	292 (51.8)	201 (35.6)	60 (10.6)	11 (2.0)	3.37	Agree
Lack of financial education at home	277 (49.1)	222 (39.4)	47 (8.3)	18 (3.2)	3.33	Agree
Poor financial attitude	217 (38.5)	289 (51.2)	41 (7.3)	17 (3.0)	3.25	Agree
Absence of financial literacy in schools' curricula	224 (39.7)	244 (43.3)	90 (16.0)	6 (1.1)	3.21	Agree
Lack of Financial Education	232 (41.1)	236 (41.8)	81 (14.4)	15 (2.7)	3.21	Agree
Too many financial products and services	262 (46.5)	179 (31.7)	104 (18.4)	19 (3.4)	3.21	Agree
Lack of Long-Term Financial Planning	229 (40.6)	201 (35.6)	110 (19.5)	24 (4.3)	3.12	Agree
Difficulty in understanding Financial Products.	228 (40.4)	179 (31.7)	122 (21.6)	35 (6.2)	3.06	Agree

Limited Financial Resources	168 (29.8)	239 (42.4)	132 (23.4)	25 (4.4)	2.97	Agree
Overall					3.21	Agree

The mean responses to the statements on perceived challenges to financial literacy are presented in Table 6 above. The table shows that the respondents agree that all constitute a challenge to financial literacy with lack of financial education constituting the biggest challenge (M=3.40) while limited financial resources is perceived as the least challenge (M=2.97). The overall mean (3.21) also indicates that respondents agree with the outlined challenges in this cluster.

Table 7: Mean Responses on Perceived Strategies that can Improve Financial Literacy among Respondents.

Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
The university should collaborate with financial institutions for internship programs, seminars	378 (67.0)	145 (25.7)	41 (7.3)	0 (0.0)	3.59	Strongly Agree
The faculties/departments should provide workshops and seminars on financial literacy.	367 (65.1)	167 (29.6)	30 (5.3)	0 (0.0)	3.59	Strongly Agree
Incorporate financial literacy courses in the curriculum	352 (62.4)	170 (30.1)	42 (7.4)	0 (0.0)	3.54	Strongly Agree
The faculties/ departments should offer online resources to teach financial literacy	337 (59.8)	193 (34.2)	34 (6.0)	0 (0.0)	3.53	Strongly Agree
The faculties/departments should establish peer mentorship programs with financially literate students	252 (44.7)	252 (44.7)	60 (10.6)	0 (0.0)	3.34	Agree
Overall					3.51	Strongly Agree

The results of the perceived strategies that can improve financial literacy are presented in Table 7. The table shows that the respondents strongly agree that all the outlined strategies are capable of improving financial literacy. The statements “the university should collaborate with financial institutions for internship programs and seminars” and “the faculties/departments should provide workshops and seminars on financial literacy” scored the highest (Mean=3.59), respectively while “the faculties/departments should establish peer mentorship programs with financially literate students” scored the lowest (M=3.34). The cluster mean (3.51) shows that the respondents strongly agree that the strategies are capable of improving financial literacy.

Discussion

The study findings on the perceived level of personal financial knowledge among the students revealed that it is at a satisfactory level. Specifically, the respondents expressed a high level of confidence in creating and maintaining a personal budget, knowledge about savings, credit, and debt management, and overall personal financial knowledge. However, while they also agree that they possess knowledge about investment and retirement planning and tax laws and regulations, these were rated slightly lower. The findings further suggest that although the understanding of personal financial knowledge is at a satisfactory level, it is foundational. They must acquire more personal financial knowledge to enable them to make good financial decisions. This is supported by Kumari (2020), who found that students who had more personal financial knowledge made good decisions relating to money management and concluded that financial literacy positively influenced the investment decisions of the students.

On the perceived level of financial behaviour among the respondents, the findings indicate that they have a strong tendency towards maintaining a savings account. This is suggestive of a high level of financial responsibility among the students, especially given the hyperinflation currently being experienced by Nigerians. The lower mean score on borrowing money for education or other expenses is instructive as it suggests a cautious approach toward debt. The findings also revealed that the respondents monitor their expenses and budget their finances regularly. These are all good financial behaviour as supported by Kamel and Sahid (2021), Paskelian et al (2019) and Zulaihati, Susanti and Widyastuti (2020) that a high level of financial literacy influences one's pattern of behaviour in decision-making. Kumai, Manju, and Kudesh (2017) posit that financial literacy is important as it enables people to avoid bankruptcy or unnecessary debts. Lusardi (2019) and Lusardi and Mitchell (2014) found that financial literacy affected saving and investment behaviour, debt management and borrowing practices. On the other hand, a low level of financial literacy affects financial behaviour. This is supported by Acheampong et al. (2015) who found that a majority of undergraduate students at the Christian Service University College, Ghana had low-level financial literacy and so were unable to make financial decisions on saving, borrowing, insurance and investment. The detrimental effect of a lack of financial literacy or low financial literacy was also revealed in a study among university students in Sri Lanka. Kumar (2020) found that the students' level of knowledge on savings was medium while their general knowledge of finance, investment, and insurance was low. The study further revealed that while a majority of the students lacked financial knowledge, students who had more knowledge of financial literacy made good decisions relating to money management in the areas of payments of fuel bills, insurance cover, repairs, and maintenance than those who did not.

The findings on whether the students believe that formal financial literacy education is important showed that a significant majority of students agree. This overwhelming agreement reinforces the fact that while the students' perceived level of personal financial knowledge is satisfactory, the perceived value of structured financial education programmes in enhancing students' financial knowledge and skills is not lost on them. It also buttresses the need for educational institutions to incorporate comprehensive financial literacy courses into their curricula. Therefore, the importance of financial education cannot be overemphasised as Andreou and Philip (2020) identified the absence of specialised personal finance course in the teaching curricula of education in Cypriots as one of the factors that affected students' knowledge of financial concepts such as savings, investments, mortgage, borrowing, inflation, planning for retirement and practical experience on money matters.

The findings on whether the students need some financial education and if they do, what topics they consider to be important to them revealed that they expressed a very high need for education on topics such as credit and debt management, saving and investing, taxes and tax planning, and entrepreneurship and business basics. While slightly lower in rating, they also expressed a need for financial education in financial goal setting, budgeting, and risk management. This indicates a substantial demand for diverse financial literacy topics and suggests that a broad and inclusive financial education program would be well-received and beneficial among the students. It also suggests that while there is a high level of agreement among the respondents on knowledge of personal finance, financial behaviour and confidence, it is not unlikely that much of what the respondents know about aspects of financial literacy may have been the result of personal experience rather than formal structured education. This reinforces the assertion by Fanta and Mutsonziwa (2014) that in most developing countries, financial literacy is rarely taught at home and in schools a situation that results in a high percentage of Nigerians and others in developing countries not being able to manage their financial resources effectively (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2018). Lusardi and Mitchell (2011), Central Bank of Nigeria (2018) and Fanta and Mutsonziwa (2014) also revealed that the absence of financial literacy curricula and the lack of exposure to financial matters during the early days of life constitute challenges to financial literacy.

On the perceived challenges to financial literacy, the results reveal a perception of multiple challenges of which lack of financial knowledge and late introduction to financial education are the most significant. Other challenges include lack of financial education at home, poor financial attitude and absence of financial literacy in schools curricula among other. These challenges have also been identified by other studies (Andreou and Philip, 2020; Central Bank of Nigeria, 2018; Mitchell and Abusheva, 2016; Fanta and Mutsonziwa, 2014; Llewellyn, 2012 and Lusardi and Mitchell, 2011). The perception of multiple challenges to financial literacy among the students highlights the need for targeted interventions to address these issues and support students in overcoming these challenges.

The findings on the perceived strategies to enhance financial literacy among the students reveal a strong agreement that the various strategies could enhance financial literacy, particularly collaboration with financial institutions for internship programs and seminars and provision of workshops and seminars by faculties. Respondents also perceived integrating financial literacy courses into the curriculum and offering online resources as effective strategies. The overall mean supports the implementation of these strategies, emphasizing the importance of institutional support and practical learning opportunities in improving financial literacy among students. In his study, Ergün, (2017) advocate that more financial literacy courses should be introduced in the university education curriculum to aid students in handling their finances better as well as improve their wellbeing. Kwenda and Sihlongonyane (2021) suggest that university authorities should provide more financial education campaigns to improve the financial management practices of students in developing countries. This is because some of the undergraduates finance their education personally through loans from banks and relatives often resulting in debts. So, there is an urgent need to teach them how to manage and service loans. Azer and Mohamad (2018) aver that academia should teach and lead students on how best to adapt to a better creditor posture. They also advised school authorities to teach financial literacy on their social media platforms since students use the platforms regularly.

The practical application of “personal finance” topics to inculcate good attitudes in students for the enhancement of appropriate financial behaviour and efficient financial decision-making and the long-term well-being of individuals has been suggested (Andreou and Philip, 2018). In the same vein, Oseifuah & Formadi (2018) advise undergraduates to acquire financial literacy, which will help them handle financial management matters by studying budgeting, interest rates, and investment, among others. Also, learning financial skills and knowledge about financial investment are thought to be among the factors that can enhance undergraduates’ investment decisions (Kumari, 2020). On their part, University Libraries, University of Maryland (2022) suggests that financial literacy topics for students should include budgeting, credit, investing, savings- banks & banking, student loans, grants, and scholarships, and other/general topics while Michigan State University Libraries (2022) outline the possible five key money topics for financial literacy to include: earn, borrow, save and invest, spend, and protect, covering all stages of life.

Conclusion

The study investigated financial literacy among the undergraduate library and information science students of the National University of Nigeria. The focus of the study was the perceived level of personal financial knowledge, perceived level of financial behaviour, perceived level of financial confidence, perception of formal financial literacy education, financial literacy topics for education, perceived challenges, and strategies to enhance financial literacy. The study revealed that the students generally possess a foundational understanding of personal finance. This was demonstrated by their confidence in budgeting and managing their finances. However, there are notable gaps, particularly in areas such as tax knowledge and investment planning. While positive financial behaviours like maintaining savings accounts and budgeting were prevalent, challenges such as lack of financial education and late introduction to financial education, among others, existed. The overwhelming

recognition of the importance of formal financial literacy education among students underscores the necessity for integrating comprehensive financial literacy programs into the educational system. This is particularly important in a developing country such as Nigeria, where financial literacy is rarely taught in homes and schools, necessitating that individuals pick up most of the knowledge they have as they engage in their daily financial affairs.

Recommendations

The study has given some insights upon which the following recommendations are made:

1. Comprehensive financial literacy courses should be developed and integrated into the undergraduate curriculum. Topics such as budgeting, saving, investing, tax planning, and debt management should be infused into the courses to provide a well-rounded understanding of financial literacy.
2. The institution can establish partnerships with financial institutions to offer internship programs, seminars, and workshops to students, which provide practical experience and real-world insights that can enhance students' financial skills and knowledge.
3. The departments and faculties should organise regular workshops and seminars on financial literacy topics, especially those areas where the students have expressed a high need for further education. This includes credit and debt management, saving and investing, and entrepreneurship.
4. The institutional library should leverage online resources and tools, such as interactive modules and financial planning software, to support and encourage self-paced learning and practical application of financial concepts among the students.

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